

Sustainable European and African Collaboration in Personalised Medicine

January 2025

Preface

This document outlines first-hand lessons learnt for Africa-Europe collaborations of the EU-Africa PerMed project¹, introduces the "Action Plan to facilitate, foster and promote personalised medicine research collaboration between Europe and Africa", and presents four major recommendations for sustainable collaborations in personalised medicine (PM):

1. Establish funding mechanisms for Africa-Europe collaborations on PM research;
2. Create the conditions for an equitable environment for Africa-Europe collaborations;
3. Identify and develop PM supporting policies;
4. Foster the organisation and collaboration at multiple levels to advance PM.

The document is addressed to global, regional, and national stakeholders, such as the European Union (EU), African Union (AU), funding bodies, non-governmental organisations (NGOs), and public-private entities. It emphasises the value of equitable partnerships to advance PM globally.

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“Personalised Medicine refers to a medical model using characterisation of individuals’ phenotypes and genotypes (e.g. molecular profiling, medical imaging, lifestyle data) for tailoring the right therapeutic strategy for the right person at the right time, and/or to determine the predisposition to disease and/or to deliver timely and targeted prevention.”²

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EU-Africa PerMed has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement No 964333.

Introduction

The EU-Africa PerMed project started its journey in February 2021, aiming to 1) integrate African countries into activities of the International Consortium for Personalised Medicine (ICPerMed) as a means to enhance the implementation of PM in the global context; 2) foster collaboration between Africa and Europe in the field of PM; and 3) strengthen Science, Technology and Innovation between the European Union and African Union (EU-AU STI) in the area of health.

Incorporating the African perspective in the global PM research agenda can contribute to reducing health inequities between countries and facilitating the access of African countries to new tools and technologies that have the potential to make healthcare more efficient and equitable.

Lessons learnt of the EU-Africa PerMed project to support other projects, programmes or initiatives that share comparable objectives include:

- 1. Collaboration does not start from scratch, it needs time for all parts to arrive to common and shared objectives:** Research or any other kind of collaboration needs time, i.e. favourable contexts have to be created, networks set up, concepts shared and equally understood, and both parts (Africa and Europe) need to be convinced, at all levels, of the value of this collaboration.
- 2. The context must be understood:** Collaborating with Africa means collaborating with 55 countries³. Africa cannot be seen as a whole because of the existence of substantial economic, cultural, social, environmental and religious differences as well as language barriers between countries even of the same African regions. Moreover, countries are at different levels of development of PM research and implementation. Different models of collaboration and instruments are needed depending on the collaborating partners and the final objective of the collaboration. There is no one-way approach for all when it comes to international or cross-border collaboration.
- 3. Africa is ready for collaboration:** Africa has a high-level research community working in PM-related areas, that can compete on equal level with their European peers when it comes to producing scientific knowledge. They could join, if funding was available, multinational research consortia working on PM. For some countries, there is a need of financial support to increase their Research and Innovation (R&I) capacity in PM and to attain a competitive position.
- 4. Different timing and levels for collaboration:** Research collaboration with low- and middle-income countries requires a long-term perspective and the co-creation of funding calls and topics of shared interest. Both Africa and Europe have to participate, top and bottom-up approaches are needed, and a shared vision of the value and benefits of the collaboration needs to be agreed upon.
- 5. International collaboration is important and valued:** International collaboration is required to advance PM implementation into healthcare. This collaboration is a must when it comes to research, but is also important, for example, for sharing international standards, safeguarding patient rights and data integrity. Platforms such as ICPerMed have been found to be an excellent way for sharing knowledge, good practice and align and encourage joint efforts in PM research and implementation. The integration of African organisations in ICPerMed will bring the African perspective into consideration to drive a true global PM agenda.
- 6. Keep the momentum going:** Creating a sustained collaborative environment for Africa-Europe collaboration in PM can start with smaller projects such as EU-Africa PerMed, but it requires a political will from both African and European decision makers, funders and already existing health research programmes to integrate PM in their strategic agendas and allocate funding for the collaboration to take place, e.g. based on policy documents as the EU-Africa PerMed Action Plan.

The EU-Africa PerMed Action Plan: A roadmap to facilitate, foster and promote personalised medicine research collaboration between Europe and Africa

The Action Plan⁴ proposes concrete recommendations in form of 26 research and research-supporting actions sorted in two overarching sections:

- **Part I: “Personalised Medicine adopting environment”** focussing on the entire “PM System of Health”
- **Part II: “Genetics and Genomics in PM”** presenting an example for a more specific PM field.

The implementation of the actions proposed will not only support the establishment of Africa-Europe collaboration but also increase the PM readiness in individual countries and regions and bring PM solutions closer to patients and public.

All actions were presented to and validated by African and European stakeholders via a consultation and a follow-up survey linked to the 3rd EU-Africa PerMed Stakeholder Workshop. The two highest ranked actions belong to the research-supporting category:

TOP 5 Research-Supporting Priorities:

1. Strengthening bioinformatics in research infrastructure (A2)
2. Support for a second edition of the EU-Africa PerMed project (A18)
3. Biobank infrastructure/cohort network (A1)
4. Capacity building of PM data generators and users (A3)
5. Education and training programme for public healthcare forces (A5)

A18 describing an “EU-Africa PerMed 2” and A19 proposing an “Africa-Europe PM Research Supporting Network” (AE PerMed). Both aim to facilitate PM communication, awareness raising, alignment of activities and strategies, and support networking activities.

PM research actions:

Topics pursued jointly e.g. via research consortia.

PM research-supporting activities:

Topics on a strategic level requiring coordinating and structuring collaborations.

All 26 actions validated as relevant; Scored an average 4.32 out of 5.

While all actions were deemed important, the EU-Africa PerMed project stakeholders have identified the five (5) top research and research-support priorities below.

TOP 5 Research Priorities:

1. Africa-Europe network for human genomic research (A25)
2. International multidisciplinary research programme addressing PM (A9)
3. Characterisation of regional genetic populations’ architecture (A24)
4. Research collaboration revealing cancer diversity (A10)
5. Research projects on companion diagnostic (A11) and on the “Big Three Infectious Diseases” and molecular based tests (A12)

Recommendations for sustainable collaboration

EU-Africa PerMed has been actively working to promote and foster a stronger and more sustained cooperation between Africa and Europe in PM. Sharing of strategies, data and standards could minimise wasteful duplication and speed progress in identifying genomics or other PM-based interventions and translate them to clinical application. Collaboration opportunities of mutual interest are outlined in the Action Plan.

To support the Action Plan implementation and in order to create more sustainable Africa-Europe collaborations in PM, EU-Africa PerMed presents in this policy brief four recommendations:

1. Establish funding mechanisms for Africa-Europe collaborations on personalised medicine research.
2. Create the conditions for an equitable environment for Africa-Europe collaborations.
3. Identify and develop personalised medicine supporting policies.
4. Foster the organisation and collaboration at multiple levels to advance personalised medicine.

International cooperation is not an option but a fundamental and inherent component of health research and innovation.

1. Establish funding mechanisms for Africa-Europe collaborations on personalised medicine research

Research in health, including PM, was and is the main driver for the understanding of diseases, the development of new and more precise diagnostics and of innovative, targeted and more effective therapies. PM research furthermore supports the prediction of therapy success, hence guide the choice of therapy as well as prevention, i.e. the risk to develop a disease. Successful PM implementation has high potential to make healthcare systems more efficient and therewith sustainable.

Budget invested in research and PM development and innovation is not to be seen as an expense (spending) but an investment in the future, i.e. research provides value.

PM is an emerging research field that requires funding on different levels: fundamental, translational and applied research, clinical studies, testing in real life setting as well as revision of already implemented approaches for their efficacy. It furthermore benefits from infrastructure development, e.g. related to sampling (biobanks), data as well as technology platforms or organisational structuring (like tumour boards as decision support).

Independent on the location (Africa or Europe), sustainable funding is required, i.e.:

- Research projects would overall benefit from longer funding durations (e.g. up to five years instead of three years, as it is current practice).
- First research discoveries need to be brought to the next level through follow-up funding mechanisms, e.g. supporting the validation of results in other settings or on larger sample sizes or continuation of networks or enlarging of research teams with stakeholders required for the next development steps, etc.
- Sustainable investment in infrastructures: Research infrastructures on national or regional level can support more than one research project and can act as centres of excellence.

Specifically, in the African context, different types of funding sources may be required:

- **African development funds of external funders**, e.g. of NGOs, global funders, European funders/the EU, to launch activities particularly in countries lacking (health) research policies.
- **National funding and funding of the AU**, allowing sustainable support to research, innovation and implementation through supportive policies.

Launch activities from bottom-up on national level with national funding and not only driven by external funding to allow direction of funding where it matters.

When engaging with low- and middle-income countries, where there is a high will to engage but resources are limited (including personnel besides funding), priorities are carefully placed and long-term perspectives are essential to engage stakeholders.

For Africa-Europe collaborations:

- **Adaptations of current (European) funding mechanisms** for joint activities, e.g. longer funding durations, consideration of additional or higher costs in Africa compared to Europe for similar activities such as purchasing of even basic consumables, change of currency value, supply issues faced particularly in Africa, etc.
- **Innovative funding approaches** are needed to increase the impact, e.g.:
 - **Joint funding activities:** National funders launch jointly transnational, centrally managed calls with their available national budget to fund their local teams in multinational research collaborations. Examples are EDCTP⁵, ERA PerMed⁶, EP PerMed⁷. This approach reduces funding in silos, avoids duplication of effort and overall increases the efficient use of available resources, knowledge and technology exchange.

- o **Capacity building:** Different settings are possible as 1) exchange programmes (students traveling to other centres), 2) on-site support for mentors (i.e. financial support to allow time allocation on mentorship activities), 3) co-mentorship from Africa and Europe, 4) train-the-trainers-programmes that form mentors and new PM “ambassadors” within the local environment and existing infrastructures instead of trainings organised in an external environment that is not corresponding to the local setting. Organisation of volunteer programmes to bring in skills and offer experience for graduates from Europe to work in Africa and at the same time foster experience programmes with African graduates to get more relative experience in an established PM healthcare setting to develop

Collaboration with Africa is not limited to providing funding for research in Africa but Europe can benefit from joint activities and learn from knowledge created in Africa.

translational medicine. Capacity building is especially needed in health and should include the younger generations, e.g. via programmes like mentorship for young girls.

- o **Funding for networking activities:** Networking activities, e.g. travel or organisation of meetings, require less funding than research projects but have a high impact. It supports the establishment of new and strengthens existing collaborations. This may lead to moving toward more cohesive strategic agendas. In the African context it may support the development of networks within one region and the connection of different regions. The setting-up of dedicated associations to sustainably foster research collaborations could be envisaged.

Support is needed to establish research networks. Already existing networks have the readiness level to respond meaningful to calls for funding when they become available.

2. Create the conditions for an equitable environment for Africa-Europe collaborations

For health research, development and innovation as well as implementation activities, a wide range of stakeholders from the public and the private sector is involved and necessary, e.g. researchers, healthcare professionals, policy makers, regulators and payers. This also includes the general population that is supposed to benefit from new health innovations like more tailored and effective PM approaches. Collaboration between different stakeholder requires trust especially in multinational endeavours.

The alignment on common principles for collaboration is a solution to create trust. Some examples are presented below:

Data sharing and ownership: The FAIR principles (2016)⁸ provide guidance for improving **F**indability, **A**ccessibility, **I**nteroperability and **R**eusability of (research) data. They have been widely accepted and adopted by a broad range of stakeholders. They allow a flexible framework, also for cross-border collaboration, and support production of high quality and standardised health data. Additional agreements like **Data Management and Data Access Agreements**⁹ are beneficial to support practical aspects around data sharing.

Novel data analysis strategies allow data mining by sharing algorithms without the need to physically share or provide access to sensitive data. This enables centres or countries to generate data and analyse locally collected samples instead of externalising this

National genome programmes allow countries to develop own data and to be ready for collaboration with neighbouring countries and internationally. The data generated on national level could be the incentive for an equal collaboration.

task, i.e. in many cases outside of the country and to the private sector. Hence, the ownership of developed data would remain in the country. This activity requires national funding.

Ethical, legal and social aspects: Health related research, and particularly in PM with aspects concerning the secondary use of data and translation of research outcome into clinical practice, requires a solid ethical, legal and social aspects (ELSA) framework.

1. Essential topics in PM to be tackled are for example: Equal access to PM independent of the location, the origin or the social status of a person;
2. Consideration of diversity when developing PM approaches (gender, age, genomics background, etc.); and
3. Consideration of cultural differences when applying and implementing PM in healthcare (e.g. closely linked to health literacy or religious background, right to know or not to know).

Why to collaborate with Europe in PM:

1. Longstanding expertise in elaborating healthy environments for cross-border collaborations in research and policies.
2. High interest in collaborating and best practices of successful collaborations.
3. High expertise in PM research, innovation and first successes in implementation.

Why to collaborate with Africa in PM:

1. Expertise available which is lacking in Europe, e.g. in the infectious disease field.
2. To complete and enlarge data sets to develop meaningful PM approaches: Considering that Africa is the origin of the human mankind and thus the most genetically diverse continent with a wide range of ethnic groups and genetic variations.

3. Identify and develop personalised medicine supporting policies

Policies can be defined as a plan of action that presents a set of activities supporting the advancements and implementation of findings in a specific field.

PM supporting policies are first steps towards an endorsing environment for development of infrastructures, research and collaboration, and leverage funding. If policies only address emerging issues there is only low support for topics preparing the future.

Example in PM: Especially in the African context, supporting policies are needed for research in genetics or biobanking as well as bioinformatics (i.e. currently there is a lack of guiding policies for managing of data collection, mining, safety, interoperability, etc.)

PM is an emerging and, for many, still unknown field that requires systemic changes or at least adaptations that involve diverse kinds of stakeholders. Furthermore, for developing PM approaches, it is essential to consider cross border collaboration, to obtain the critical mass of data needed to develop meaningful and broadly applicable tools or drugs.

Europe has shown over the past years that jointly developed policies can push fields like PM (fig.1). A first PM specific Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (PerMed SRIA) was published in 2015. This SRIA was transformed into a roadmap - the Action Plan (2017), brought into action via a newly formed European strategic platform, the ICPeMed (2016) and a joint multinational funding initiative, the ERA PerMed (2017-2023, approx. 130M€).

A new SRIA for PM (2023) is the backbone of an even larger initiative, the European Partnership for Personalised Medicine (EP PerMed, 2023-2033, approx. 375M€) that aligns funding and strategic activities of nearly all European countries and associated countries. Comparable activities were launched in Europe focussing on genomics (1+MG Roadmap 2020-2022¹⁰) or health data (A European strategy for data, 2020¹¹).

Figure 1: The development of strategies supporting Personalised Medicine in Europe since 2015.

The World Health Organisation (WHO) has very recently released (November 2024) “New principles for ethical human genomic data collection and sharing”¹² to “establish a global approach to help protect individual rights, promote equity and foster responsible collaboration in genomic research.”

Africa seems to be lagging in PM implementation, with countries at different levels of PM growth. Already, discussions regarding uptake of PM tools to fight the huge burden of diseases in the continent are taking shape. The AUDA NEPAD has published an important Framework for Implementation of Genomic Medicine for Public Health in Africa (2021), and WHO “accelerating access to genomics for global health” (2022). Important, also in the growth of PM, is that the 2016 EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) has spurred increased regulation and governance of personal data in Africa, with AU and regional bodies such as the Economic Community of West African States (ECOWAS) and Southern African Development Community (SADC) developing model data protection laws to inform sharing of data among member states and serving as a key reference in development of country specific data protection laws.

The adaptation and implementation of PM policies at regional and national levels will be essential for the advancement and maturity of PM in Africa. This will require benchmarking and collaborations with developed nations such as Europe, which has a vibrant PM environment. An important step for Africa-Europe collaboration in PM is the AU-EU Innovation Agenda¹³ (2023) in which “precision” medicine is mentioned as essential long-term action in public health.

While PM could be seen as a long-term objective, PM supporting policies are needed now to pave the way for future implementation and accessibility of personalised care.

4. Foster the organisation and collaboration at multiple levels to advance personalised medicine

PM is a topic which addresses the entire system of health and requires a systemic approach and structuring efforts on different levels, i.e. structuration on local level and cross-border collaboration (fig. 2):

- National (country) level and sometimes even more granular e.g. on the level of National Regions within a country, i.e. the level that coordinates healthcare as well as educational activities.
- Collaboration between different countries, for example regional organisation of neighbouring countries of the same area within a continent (e.g. southern, northern, east, west and central African region) or between different continents (Mediterranean countries) or bilateral agreements based on common interests.
- Inter-regional collaboration or collaboration on continental level.
- Global collaboration, e.g. between Africa and Europe as well as worldwide.

PM requires collaboration on all of the above levels, while the activities differ in granularity and timing:

Short-term goals: 1) Organisation at the country level, e.g. through established and regularly animated national PM hubs or “mirror groups”, to support developing of national strategies considering or dedicated to PM and foster PM research and innovation collaboration at country level; 2) Individual countries of Africa and Europe that are ready for cross-border collaborations can join already running initiatives. Those countries could be seen in their regional context (neighbouring countries) as regional champions and could bring forward and represent besides the national perspective the regional ones.

Medium-term goal: Fostering collaboration between neighbouring countries to develop the PM environment with more advanced countries, within each region in Africa. Some countries are already engaged in international collaborations or have achieved a high level of PM readiness to advocate and be tasked at regional level to support regional collaboration as “regional champions” and share policy, infrastructure and develop a workforce in neighbouring countries lacking similar resources.

Figure 2: PM requires an organisation at country level. Different countries can collaborate (green arrows), e.g. bilaterally or countries with high readiness level can join existing collaboration and act at the same time as “regional champions”. Regional collaboration, e.g. animated by regional champions and between neighbouring countries, can foster building of networks. Interregional collaboration lead to continental and international programmes.

Well advanced countries will benefit from cross-country and inter-regional collaboration (e.g. understand diverse populations that exist in their own countries) and at the same time, the inclusion of under resourced countries just starting their journey in the PM field is ensured and they are empowered.

Long-term goal: National PM strategies, regional (neighbouring country) networks as well as global collaboration (e.g. between Africa and Europe) are in place. These three elements foster the development of a PM endorsing policy environment locally, regional coordination and enable sustainable partnerships with other countries or regions in the same continent and worldwide.

Identification of regional champions in Southern, North, West, East and Central Africa can push the regional developments, the creation of local networks and allow cross regional/continental collaboration as well as immediate outreach to joint African and European collaborations.

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Imprint

Funding information

The Coordination and Support Action (CSA) EU-Africa PerMed has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the grant agreement No. 964333.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare no competing interest for this work.

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Acknowledgement

The authors thank all members of Work Package 3 for developing and contributing to the Policy Brief. Furthermore, the authors of this paper would like to thank the EU-Africa PerMed consortium, the advisory board and all experts who have participated in the diverse EU-Africa PerMed consultation activities.

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Publisher

INNOVATEC, Ronda de Valdecarrizo 41B. 28760, Tres Cantos (Madrid)

Date

January 2025

Using the content and citation

If you wish to use some of the written content, please refer to: "Policy Brief: Sustainable European and African collaboration in Personalised Medicine. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14745173>".